

Predicting Students' Learning Styles in An Educational Digital Game System Using Support Vector Machines

Agbonifo, O. C. and Femi-Falade, M. O.

Department of Information Systems and Department of Computer Science

Federal University of Technology, Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria.

ocagbonifo@futa.edu.ng and maryfemifalade@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: maryfemifalade@gmail.com, +2348160901445

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Abstract

Games play a vital role in human culture and society, fostering motivation and engagement. This is why the principles of gaming, such as gamification and interactive design, are being applied in various non-gaming settings like schools, healthcare, and consumer behaviour to improve motivation, behaviour, and learning outcome. This study aims to predict students' learning style preferences based on their behaviour in an educational digital game system using the Support Vector Machines. A dataset extracted from the Jowilder competition on the Kaggle platform is used to train a Support Vector Machines classifier, which identifies learning style preferences. Hyperparameter optimization is performed using kernel function tuning to enhance model accuracy. The Support Vector Machines model is trained using different kernels-Linear, Polynomial, and Radial Basis Function to verify which approach works best for classification. The assessment of the model using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score indicates that the Radial Basis Function kernel performs the best, achieving a high accuracy. This study reveals that gameplay behaviour can provide a reasonable predictor for learning styles, opening up new opportunities for personalized learning paths in serious gaming environments.

Keywords: educational digital games, learning styles, students' behaviour, support vector machines, personalised learning paths

INTRODUCTION

Modern technologies have a significant impact on every industry, including gaming and education. It is very important to observe how the education system has advanced in relation to gaming (De Carvalho & Coelho, 2022). A game is a type of activity that is interactive and obsessive as it has specific rules and one or more objectives (Daoudi, 2022; Min *et al.* 2022; Becker, 2021). Success can be measured and there is an ending (Min *et al.*, 2022). Video gaming is one of the largest industries in the world today and in 2020 it video gaming generated around \$114 billion (Ullah *et al.*, 2022). This is a result of the tremendous amount of time and effort that gamers devote towards this activity. Research studies regarding the impact of games on education has increased over the years (Ullah *et al.*, 2022). All these research studies showed that adopting a game-based learning

approach impacts people more and children in particular. Lack of motivation due to traditional teaching and learning practices prevalent in higher education is one of the major reasons for student dropout given in literature, (Gomez & Suárez, 2020). There is a clear need to develop systems that can capture the attention of students.

Serious gaming is the application of video games towards achievement of objectives outside the sphere of entertainment (Bontchev *et al.* 2021). Serious games or applied games are defined under the scope of the defense, health care, emergency management, education, sports, exploration, city planning, engineering, and even politics (Maheu-Cadotte *et al.*, 2021). For many years, games have captured the attention of children, and they have served as an important tool for improving the learning experience. Recently, however, the adult population has also managed to embrace it (Mohanty *et al.*, 2021). Today, the teaching and learning process in schools relies on the use of educational technology to provide learners with greater opportunities to enhance their skills and competencies (Prasad *et al.*, 2022). In this context, teaching tools such as Serious Educational Games (SEG) and Learning Analytics (LA) are now increasingly being considered by educators and researchers, who believe these tools, may improve the educational experience (Daoudi, 2022).

Coleman and Money (2020) argue that understanding the educational impact and untapped opportunities of digital video games is a prerequisite for realizing their full potential, and recent research highlights growing interest in how gamified content can boost affect, motivation, behaviour change, and learning. However, the psychological mechanisms underlying gamification remain under-explored (Yu *et al.*, 2021), and several scholars identify low student engagement in traditional e-learning systems as a gap that gamification could fill. The most prominent problem with gamified elements is their failure to generate active will among learners (Hassan *et al.*, 2021). Effective teaching and learning depend on identifying each learner's preferred style and modality (Cabual, 2021); while some students have a single dominant style, others draw on a range of styles depending on context. Consequently, a framework that detects students' learning styles from their system interactions and tailors gamified experiences accordingly is essential.

Most existing studies focus on traditional e-learning environments, where other learning style models such as Felder-Silverman are used to personalize static content. However, Gregorc model's two-dimensional, process-focused framework maps more cleanly onto the interactive, adaptive nature of digital games, that can provide richer behavioural data. Yet, few studies have leveraged this potential to infer students' learning styles. Additionally, current approaches often rely on self-reported questionnaires to classify learning styles, which are subject to bias and may not accurately reflect how students interact with game content. There is limited work on using interaction log data from educational games to automatically predict learning styles, despite the fact that such data could enable real-time personalization without disrupting gameplay. Moreover, while various machine learning algorithms have been employed in educational data mining, the application of Support Vector Machines, known for their robustness in high-dimensional spaces and ability to handle datasets effectively, has not been extensively explored in this specific context.

Thus, this research seeks to fill these gaps by utilizing log-based behavioural features extracted from an educational digital game to predict a model using Gregorc learning style dimensions. In addition, the effectiveness of SVM classifiers for learning style prediction in the gaming context will be evaluated. By addressing these under-researched areas, this study aims to contribute a novel perspective to the personalization of game-based learning through data-driven methods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopts a quantitative research design to predict students' learning styles in a digital educational game environment. The methodology integrates unsupervised learning (K-Means clustering) with a supervised classification technique (Support Vector Machines) to predict learning style groups based on interaction data. The focus is on applying the Gregorc Learning Style Model, which classifies learners into four cognitive styles: Concrete Sequential, Abstract Sequential, Concrete Random, and Abstract Random.

Data Collection

The dataset used for this research was extracted from Kaggle machine learning site as comma separated values (CSV) from the results of the Jowilder online learning game system designed to support learning through interactive scenarios. The dataset includes log files detailing student interactions, such as click patterns, time spent on tasks, navigation paths, and textual input. Each record corresponds to a user session and contains multiple variables capturing behavioural and contextual features. The pre-processed dataset consisted of 3,728 entries, 21 columns which contained session data, event tracking, coordinates, and metadata. Importantly, some columns like page, hover_duration, text, fqid had many missing values. Also, there was no direct column indicating "learning style". The three primary tasks accomplished at this stage were; drop columns that are mostly null or irrelevant, encode categorical features and normalize numeric values. The complete pre-processing step of feature selection was aimed at improving the learning accuracy of the model by removing redundant features, irrelevant data, and noisy data as well as minimizing the model's training time. There were no significant missing values in the features of the dataset except for the two features which happened to be "fqid" (the fully qualified ID of the event) and "hover_duration" (how long in milliseconds the hover happened).

Clustering with K-Means

K-Means clustering was employed to identify patterns in student behaviour that could correspond to distinct learning style groups. The optimal number of clusters was determined using the elbow method, and the resulting clusters were interpreted in the context of Gregorc's framework. Each learner session was then assigned to one of the four groups based on the clustering output.

K-means classification operation was executed based on the following steps:

- i. Determine the value of K (the number of clusters) and initial guesses for the centroids.
- ii. Calculate the distance d from each data point X_i at $(X_{i1}, \dots, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{in})$ to each centroid q which includes q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n using equation 1

$$d(X_i - q) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (X_{ij} - q_j)^2} \quad (1)$$

- iii. Assign each data point to the closest centroid, establishing an association that defines the initial k clusters.
- iv. Compute the centroid for each newly defined cluster, which is the center of the mass of the data points within the cluster using equation 2.

$$q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m S_{i1}}{m}, \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m S_{i2}}{m}, \dots, \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m S_{in}}{m} \quad (2)$$

- v. Repeat steps ii, iii, iv until the algorithm converges to the final solution

Classification with Support Vector Machines

After establishing cluster-based groupings, a Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier was trained to predict the learning style category from the original set of behavioural features. The data was divided into training and testing sets using a 70:30 split (2,609 rows belonged to the training set and 1118 rows to the testing set). Standardization was applied to the feature set to ensure comparability across variables. The SVM model was implemented with a linear kernel due to its suitability for high-dimensional, sparse data. Hyperparameters were tuned using cross-validation to optimize model performance. Model evaluation was conducted using k-fold cross-validation with $k = 5$, which provides a balance between bias and variance for datasets of moderate size. The dataset was randomly shuffled prior to splitting, and a fixed random seed (`random_state = 42`) was used throughout to ensure reproducibility. The linear kernel was initially selected as a baseline model due to its computational efficiency and interpretability. This initial choice allowed for a transparent assessment of whether a simple linear decision boundary was sufficient to model the relationship between game telemetry features and learning style classes. Subsequently, a comparative evaluation was conducted using non-linear kernels, specifically the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel, to capture potential non-linear interactions in learner behaviour. Cross-validation results demonstrated that the RBF kernel consistently outperformed the linear kernel across all folds, indicating that the relationship between interaction patterns and learning styles was non-linear in nature. Consequently, the RBF kernel was selected as the final model.

Model Evaluation

The performance of the SVM classifier was evaluated using standard classification metrics, including:

Accuracy: the overall correctness of the model,

Precision and Recall: to assess the model's reliability across classes,

F1 Score: to balance precision and recall,

Confusion Matrix: to visualize misclassification patterns across learning styles.

These metrics provided a comprehensive view of how well the predictive model captured the underlying behavioural distinctions among the learning style groups.

Kernel Comparison

In order to find the best SVM parameters, the model was trained with three different kernel functions: Linear, Polynomial (degree=3), and Radial Basis Function (RBF). The classification accuracy and F1-score were used to evaluate the performance of each kernel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of training prediction with the student learning style predicted from behavioral data in the digital game system using the proposed machine learning framework. The analysis is structured according to the outcomes of the clustering, the predictive ability of the

SVM classifier, and how these findings were interpreted in relation to Gregorc's learning style model. Importantly, some columns like page, hover_duration, text, fqid had many missing values so the columns were dropped.

The Gregorc Learning Style Model was selected over other frameworks such as Felder–Silverman and Kolb because of its strong alignment with observable, low-level behavioural telemetry generated in digital game environments. Gregorc’s model categorises learners along two orthogonal dimensions; perception (Concrete vs. Abstract) and ordering (Sequential vs. Random) which map directly to in-game behaviours such as navigation order, task completion sequences, exploration patterns, and response regularity. Missing values were handled using a context-appropriate imputation strategy. For page and fqid, missing entries were treated as a distinct category (“Unknown”) to preserve interaction semantics. For hover_duration, missing values were imputed using the median, which is robust to skewed distributions commonly observed in interaction time data. This approach minimised information loss while avoiding bias introduced by listwise deletion. In addition to raw counts, the confusion matrix was normalised by row (actual class) to improve interpretability. Table 1 shows the percentages that indicate the proportion of instances of each actual class correctly or incorrectly classified.

Table 1: Percentages of the instances of each actual class correctly or incorrectly classified

Actual \ Predicted	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Cluster 0	87.8%	7.3%	2.4%	2.4%
Cluster 1	2.6%	97.4%	0.0%	0.0%
Cluster 2	2.4%	9.8%	87.8%	0.0%
Cluster 3	2.4%	2.4%	0.0%	95.1%

These results indicate strong diagonal dominance, demonstrating high class-specific predictive performance, particularly for Clusters 0 and 2.

A key limitation of this study is that the dataset acquired from a single Kaggle competition, representing interaction patterns within one specific educational-game context. As a result, the behavioural signatures learned by the model may reflect game-specific mechanics, narrative structure, and cultural assumptions embedded in that environment. Interaction patterns may differ across games with alternative pedagogical designs, genres, or player demographics. This study utilised secondary, anonymised data obtained from a publicly available Kaggle dataset. No personally identifiable information was accessed or processed. As such, formal institutional ethical approval was not required. Nevertheless, the study adhered to ethical principles of data minimisation, confidentiality, and responsible use of learner interaction data, in line with established guidelines for educational data mining research.

Where model evaluation involved repeated runs or cross-validation, performance metrics were summarised using mean \pm standard deviation to reflect variability across folds. This provides a more reliable estimate of model stability than single-split evaluation. Where applicable, confidence intervals further contextualise performance uncertainty and support the robustness of the reported results.

K-Means Clustering

The normalized extracted behaviour features were passed through the K-Means clustering algorithm to reveal clusters with similar behaviour. In order to determine the optimal number of clusters, the elbow method was employed. The elbow curve suggested a subtle inflection at $k = 4$, which aligns well with the four cognitive categories defined by the Gregorc model. The result of the elbow method for clustering is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Elbow Method for Optimal k

A close examination of the cluster centroids also revealed clear behavioural patterns and learning styles that classified each learner's session into one of the four Gregorc learning styles. The results of the clustering are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Mapping of the Clusters to the learning style dimensions

Cluster	Characteristics	Learning Style Dimension
Cluster 0	High structure, frequent short interactions, low exploration	Concrete Sequential
Cluster 1	Medium-interaction and skips content	Abstract Sequential.
Cluster 2	Tactile, kinaesthetic experience with irregular pace	Concrete random
Cluster 3	Large variability of navigation and emotional dialogue interaction	Abstract Random.

Support Vector Machines Classification

The labeled dataset was then used to train an SVM model using the RBF which predicted the learning style dimension from the initial behavioural features. The classifier was evaluated using

a hold-out dataset containing 30% of the population. A confusion matrix was presented to gain more information regarding the class-wise performance. Support in this case is the number of actual samples in that class and this helps to explain the confidence by numbers indicated by score values for precision and recall. The confusion matrix for the SVM (RBF Kernel) is shown in Table 3. Performance metrics based on confusion matrix data (macro-averaged over all the classes). The classification results are shown in Table 4.

Table 3: Confusion Matrix

Actual \ Predicted	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Cluster 0	36	3	1	1
Cluster 1	2	75	0	0
Cluster 2	1	4	36	0
Cluster 3	1	1	0	39

Table 4: Classification Results

Cluster	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.90	0.88	0.89	41
1	0.90	0.97	0.94	77
2	0.97	0.88	0.92	41
3	0.98	0.95	0.96	41
Accuracy	0.93			200
Macro Avg	0.94	0.92	0.93	200
Weighted Avg	0.93	0.93	0.93	200

Most errors made between the Abstract Sequential and the Abstract Random groups, were identified by the confusion matrix, which is expected due to their conceptual similarity in the Gregorc model. In the same vein, they both accounted for the highest clarity in classification, likely due to its distinct, rule-bound interaction style.

The results demonstrate that behavioural data from a digital game can reliably indicate learners' cognitive preferences. The combination of unsupervised and supervised learning methods proved effective in: uncovering meaningful clusters aligned with theoretical learning styles, building a predictive model with strong generalization capabilities. This suggests that it is feasible to support real-time, adaptive learning experiences based on automated style detection without requiring learners to complete questionnaires. Moreover, the accuracy and balance of the SVM classifier validate its suitability for educational applications involving high-dimensional, behavioural datasets.

In addition, in order to find the best SVM parameters, the model was trained with three different kernel functions: Linear, Polynomial (degree=3), and Radial Basis Function (RBF). The classification accuracy was used to evaluate the performance of each kernel. This is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Comparison of the Kernel functions Accuracy

Kernel	Accuracy
Linear	0.88
Polynomial	0.89
Radial Basis Function	0.93

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Overall, this research bridges the gap between machine learning and personalised education by proposing and validating a multilevel predictive model for learning styles in serious-game environments. The outcomes could enhance both theoretical and practical knowledge in the domain of AI-driven educational systems.

The results confirmed that students' gameplay behaviours contain meaningful signals that correlate with cognitive learning preferences. The SVM model demonstrated strong predictive accuracy, with particularly high reliability in identifying structured (Concrete Sequential) and exploratory (Concrete Random) learner types.

Thus, based on the insights gained from this research, several recommendations are offered for future research. This includes the integration of machine learning modules that can continuously monitor and analyse learner behaviour into Adaptive Learning Systems and expansion to other learning models. While the Gregorc model provided a useful cognitive framework for this study, future systems could be designed to accommodate multiple learning style theories (Kolb and Felder-Silverman) for comparison. This could offer a more comprehensive view of how different frameworks perform in dynamic learning contexts.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates that machine learning can play a vital role in identifying and responding to students' individual learning styles in digital education environments. As educational systems move toward more personalized experiences, predictive models as proposed in this research which offer a promising path forward for enhancing both learner experience and academic success.

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